

The Seed as Instrument: Agricultural Regulation, Knowledge, and the Colonial Subject in West Africa

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Abstract

This paper argues that colonial seed programmes in West Africa did more than introduce new crop varieties. They also transferred regulatory authority, reorganised agrarian knowledge, and helped produce colonial subjects. Building on Jane Guyer’s account of shifting regulatory models in Britain and Nigeria, I argue that these models were not merely delayed or imperfectly copied in colonial settings. They were selectively reworked to serve imperial priorities, above all commodity extraction, administrative oversight, and the remaking of local agricultural practice. Drawing on Christophe Bonneuil’s study of peanut breeding in Senegal, Susannah Chapman’s analysis of rice innovation in The Gambia, and archival evidence from the potato scheme in Northern Nigeria, I show that the seed became a concentrated site where regulatory ambition, scientific expertise, and local knowledge met under unequal conditions. The result was not a coherent transfer of metropolitan governance but a form of colonial regulatory incoherence: a durable arrangement in which imported models were only partially implemented, redirected away from local welfare, and sustained through the suppression or appropriation of existing agrarian systems. The paper makes an important contribution to several different literatures, including the history of colonial agriculture, the history of agricultural biopolitics, technoscientific and regulatory interventions into living materials, and the history of plant breeding.

Keywords: colonial agriculture; seed regulation; West Africa; agrarian knowledge; empire; varietal innovation

Introduction

In 1938, the head of the Agriculture Department in French West Africa remarked that the distribution of improved seed offered the fastest and simplest means of “penetrat[ing] the Natives” (Bonneuil 1999, 294). The statement is unusually direct, but the underlying logic was not unique to French Senegal. Across colonial West Africa, agricultural science treated seed as more than a biological input. Seed was also a regulatory object: a means of extending expert authority into rural life, reorganising cultivation, and binding farmers to imperial systems of production and exchange. Whether in peanut schemes in Senegal, potato production on the Jos Plateau, or rice cultivation in The Gambia, seed programmes served as mechanisms through which colonial states sought to render agrarian societies legible, governable, and productive on metropolitan terms.

Jane Guyer's analysis of food regulation in Britain and Nigeria provides the conceptual point of departure for this argument. Guyer shows that modern regulation in Britain developed through overlapping models rather than through neat succession: first a regime centred on purity and uniformity, then a welfare-oriented model consolidated in wartime, and later a broader social-cost framework (Guyer 1993, 799–803). These models did not displace one another completely. Instead, each left institutional and conceptual residues that could be reassembled elsewhere. In colonial contexts, Guyer argues, such models were transferred unevenly, generating what she calls “evolutionary parallelism”: the selective application of older regulatory forms to societies positioned as developmentally behind Britain itself (Guyer 1993, 804–806). Yet the cases considered here suggest that unevenness alone does not fully capture the character of regulatory transfer. What emerges instead is a more structural pattern in which imported regulatory logics were stripped of the institutional arrangements that made them meaningful in Europe and reoriented toward extraction, surveillance, and administrative control.

This paper extends Guyer's argument in three ways. First, it treats seeds not merely as objects regulated by the state but as key vehicles through which regulatory models travelled and were remade. Second, it argues that the incompleteness of colonial transfer was not accidental or transitional; it was constitutive of colonial rule, allowing expert knowledge to incorporate selected local practices while subordinating the social worlds from which those practices emerged. Third, it brings into view forms of labour, value, and innovation that colonial and postcolonial regulatory systems repeatedly marginalised, including women's seed work, household storage, and spiritually grounded understandings of varietal change. Taken together, these cases show that colonial regulation did not fail because it fell short of metropolitan ideals. It operated according to a different logic, one in which welfare language, scientific authority, and developmental ambition were mobilised without the institutional commitments necessary to serve colonial subjects.

Purity, Pedigree, and the Colonial Seed

Guyer identifies purity and uniformity as the first major modern regulatory model in Britain (Guyer 1993, 799–800). Emerging through the Adulteration Acts of the 1860s and 1875, this model positioned the state as an arbiter between producers and consumers by relying on inspection, licensing, and prosecution to prevent adulteration. Its primary concern was the integrity of commodities in circulation.

Bonneuil's account of the Bambey Station in Senegal shows how this model was transformed in a colonial context (Bonneuil 1999, 286–290). Plant breeding at Bambey began in 1924 and initially relied less on Mendelian genetics than on pedigree selection aimed at producing uniform, classifiable peanut varieties for circulation through the Sociétés Indigènes de Prévoyance. Purity, in this setting, was not simply a technical criterion. It was a regulatory ideal that made seeds easier to measure, distribute, and supervise.

The colonial meaning of purity, however, differed fundamentally from its metropolitan counterpart. In Britain, purity regulation was directed against fraudulent traders in the name of consumer protection. In Senegal, it was directed at farmers themselves: at mixed local seed

stocks, volunteer plants, and cultivation practices adapted to ecological variability. Bonneuil's "indigenous farm" was therefore not an empirical recognition of local farming on its own terms but a controlled site through which colonial science translated selected practices into administratively legible knowledge. Farmers became visible as sources of data only once they had been reorganised as subjects of intervention (Bonneuil 1999, 291–296).

This point sharpens Guyer's notion of "evolutionary parallelism" (Guyer 1993, 804–806). Colonial regulation did not simply reproduce an older British model in delayed form; it repurposed that model. Purity ceased to protect consumers and instead disciplined producers for imperial supply. The same inversion is visible in the Nigerian potato scheme. There, imported seed potatoes, grading systems, and distribution controls reproduced the institutional form of purity regulation, but without any commitment to local food security. Agricultural research in Nigeria commenced with the establishment of a botanical research station in Lagos in 1893 (NNAK, C.G. Ames, *The Gazetteers of Plateau Province*, 1932). Potatoes were cultivated primarily for European miners, missionaries, officials, and soldiers, and the selected varieties were chosen for imperial demand and temperate performance rather than for Nigerian agrarian conditions (Akpu n.d.). When the colonial government launched its potato production drive in 1931, it was explicitly to address the difficulty European personnel had obtaining potatoes (Goshit, 2000).

Potato production in Nigeria illuminates the broader dynamics of colonial agricultural regulation. Agricultural experimentation in northern Nigeria expanded from 1923, when the colonial government established a 150-acre farm centre in Kano; in 1924, a botanist was posted to the Department of Agriculture headquarters at Samaru near Zaria (Steele 1967, 35). In Yola and Numan, where a substantial European population sought familiar food supplies, colonial officials identified potatoes as a strategic crop. Earlier potato varieties cultivated in Bamenda, introduced under German rule in the 1890s, were considered unsatisfactory in both taste and yield after years without fresh seed. Against this background, imperial officials treated the breeding and importation of new potato varieties as a matter of practical and administrative importance. The colonial state therefore initiated trials with seed potatoes imported from England, Ireland, and Scotland and distributed them experimentally to farmers, district heads, and village heads. Potatoes entered colonial Nigeria through a combination of imperial planning, missionary cultivation, local experimentation, and ecological uncertainty. Colonial officials viewed the crop as a promising highland commodity and promoted trials of imported seed varieties from Britain, Ireland, continental Europe, South Africa, the Canary Islands, and the United States. Mission stations cultivated potatoes in kitchen gardens, schools, vocational centres, and religious houses, thereby serving as local sites of experimentation and distribution. African farmers, however, engaged these new agricultural possibilities selectively, adapting them to existing agrarian routines, labour systems, market opportunities, and environmental risks rather than simply adopting them on colonial terms.

Local farmers were initially resistant, believing the crop to be poisonous; their subsequent incorporation into potato growing was achieved through "demonstration, economic incentives, or coercion" (Akpu, n.d.). The seed potatoes imported from England, Scotland, Ireland, and

eventually the United States were not selected for their suitability to Nigerian agroecological conditions; they were selected for their acceptability to European palates and their performance under temperate conditions. The *Great Scott*, *Arran Victory*, *Up-to-Date* — varieties with their own genealogies in Irish and Scottish plant breeding — arrived in Nigeria bearing the epistemic authority of metropolitan science and the market power of the colonial economy.

What is striking about the potato case is the extent to which the regulatory apparatus that emerged around seed supply — the Importation of Plants Regulation of 1947, the revolving seed supply scheme, the grading stations, the price controls — reproduced the purity model not as a protection of Nigerian consumers but as a management of supply chains for European consumption and wartime military provisioning. The concern with virus-free seed was real and scientifically grounded; late blight had devastated Irish potato production in the nineteenth century and was advancing through the Belgian Congo. But the regulatory response prioritized the integrity of the imperial seed circuit over the development of locally adapted varieties. As Akpu notes, "the most economical and practical solution remained frequent importations of fresh seeds from overseas" — a judgment that simultaneously acknowledged the limitations of local multiplication and reproduced the dependency that made those limitations permanent.

The potato case makes the broader logic especially clear. Regulatory concern with virus-free seed, grading, and controlled importation was real, but it served the stability of imperial commodity circuits rather than the needs of Nigerian cultivators or consumers. In this respect, the colonial seed scheme did not represent a failed approximation of metropolitan regulation. It represented a coherent imperial adaptation of that regulation for extraction, dependence, and external supply (Akpu n.d.).

Welfare without Welfare Institutions

Guyer's second regulatory model emerged from wartime Britain and centred on state provision shaped by nutritional science, differentiated need, and sustained institutional coordination among public authorities, producers, and consumers (Guyer 1993, 800–803). Its significance lay not only in the language of necessity and supply but also in the infrastructure that made welfare administration possible.

In Nigeria, Guyer shows, this model was invoked but not institutionally reproduced (Guyer 1993, 806–812). The essential commodities programme of the early 1970s adopted the vocabulary of national supply and public necessity, yet it lacked the corporatist and administrative structures that underpinned welfare regulation in Britain. The result was not weakened social provision but a different political arrangement in which access to basic goods became concentrated in a narrow set of intermediaries. In that context, the language of welfare masked the consolidation of distributive power rather than the protection of citizens.

Bonneuil's analysis of the Sociétés Indigènes de Prévoyance reveals an earlier colonial version of this dynamic (Bonneuil 1999, 289–294). These organisations were presented as protective institutions, offering seed loans and buffering rural households against scarcity. In practice, however, they also secured the continued cultivation of export crops, reinforced local hierarchies, and extended colonial administration into everyday agrarian life. Their

significance lies precisely in this duality: they mobilised the language of support while binding farmers more tightly to systems of obligation and oversight.

A crucial element of this transformation was the removal of seed from household storage and its relocation into monitored circuits of repayment and redistribution (Bonneuil 1999, 289–294). Once the seed passed through official channels, it became legible to the state as a measurable and administrable object. What had previously been embedded in domestic practice and ecological adaptation was converted into an item of record, debt, and periodic allocation. Colonial seed policy therefore did not merely alter distribution; it redefined the terms under which agrarian reproduction could occur.

The consequences were epistemic as well as economic. As seed circulation moved into state-managed systems, established practices of saving, selecting, and exchanging diverse stocks were displaced by an emphasis on uniformity, repayment, and externally defined improvement. Mixed farming systems adapted to varied soils and risks were gradually subordinated to monocrop production oriented toward export. The effect was not simply technical standardisation but a narrowing of the social and ecological conditions in which local agricultural judgment could operate (Bonneuil 1999, 291–296).

Chapman’s account of rice cultivation in Jarra West demonstrates the long afterlife of this distinction (Chapman 2022, 164–166). By 2010, one village maintained fifty-four rice varieties, while peanuts numbered only three. That contrast reflects differential exposure to regulatory and commercial pressures. Men’s peanut production had long been drawn into export-oriented systems of pricing, seed control, and agronomic oversight. Women’s rice cultivation, by contrast, remained only partially incorporated into these circuits, leaving greater scope for experimentation, exchange, and varietal maintenance beyond formal state attention.

That relative autonomy, however, was not secure. As national seed policy and regional intellectual property frameworks such as the Arusha Protocol extended formal criteria of ownership, innovation, and recognition, practices sustained through women’s labour and local social relations became increasingly difficult to register within official categories. The problem was not merely legal exclusion but the imposition of legal forms that could recognise innovation only by abstracting it from the relational worlds that produced it (Chapman 2022, 166–170).

Invisible Labour, Innovation, and Epistemic Violence

Chapman’s central intervention is to show how Mandinka rice farmers in Jarra West understand varietal change as the outcome of relations among human labour, moral character, spiritual agency, and the cultivated field (Chapman 2022, 163–168). Off-types are not treated simply as biological anomalies. They may instead be understood as gifts mediated through jinn and divine favour, received by farmers whose conduct and fields make such emergence possible. The subsequent work of stabilising and naming a new variety is therefore not reducible to selection alone; it is also moral, social, and aesthetic labour.

This account is not merely a cultural gloss on processes that could otherwise be described in genetic terms. It describes an economy of innovation: a system for allocating credit, generating

obligation, and sustaining the relations through which varietal diversity persists (Chapman 2022, 167–170). Within this framework, spiritual recognition and social recognition are inseparable. To receive an off-type is to be marked as a person of standing; to name a variety after oneself is to enter a circuit of reciprocity through which value returns over time. What is at stake, then, is not only how new varieties emerge but also how innovation itself is understood, authorised, and distributed.

Such an economy of innovation poses a direct challenge to the regulatory worlds described by Guyer, Bonneuil, and Akpu. Colonial agricultural science treated heterogeneity as a defect to be eliminated rather than as a condition of adaptive practice. Volunteer plants, mixed seed stocks, and agroecological relationships such as those involving *Faidherbia albida* appeared within expert discourse primarily as obstacles to purity, standardisation, and control (Bonneuil 1999, 286–296; Chapman 2022, 163–170).

Bonneuil's account makes visible the epistemic violence embedded in this process (Bonneuil 1999, 291–296). The suppression of heterogeneity was not only an agronomic decision; it was also a decision about what could count as agricultural knowledge and who could produce it. Sereer farmers who managed soil fertility through *Faidherbia albida*, adjusted sowing dates to climatic variability, and maintained landraces adapted to different soils were generating sophisticated agrarian knowledge. Yet that knowledge became legible to colonial scientists only when extracted from its social and ecological context and translated into the categories of formal experimentation. Chapman's farmers illuminate precisely what this translation excludes: forms of knowing that are relational, situated, and distributed across human and more-than-human actors (Chapman 2022, 167–170). When such accounts are redescribed merely as incomplete understandings of biological mechanisms, the analytic frame reproduces the hierarchy of knowledge established by colonial science.

This comparison also clarifies the meaning of regulatory failure. For Guyer, the breakdown of colonial and postcolonial regulatory systems undermined the moral authority of the state by exposing corruption, mismanagement, and institutional weakness (Guyer 1993, 812–815). Chapman identifies a deeper problem: regulatory systems fail not only when they are corrupt, but when they cannot perceive the social relations that sustain innovation and diversity in the first place (Chapman 2022, 166–170). Legal regimes centred on certification, breeders' rights, and intellectual property presume a bounded inventor and a stabilised product. They are therefore poorly equipped to recognise collective, iterative, and relational forms of agricultural creativity. The archival silence surrounding the Nigerian potato scheme reinforces this point. Farmers appear only intermittently, and mostly through colonial interpretations that cast hesitation as superstition and acceptance as the effect of demonstration or propaganda. The possibility that cultivators evaluated potatoes on their own terms remains largely absent from the record, revealing the narrow evidentiary frame within which colonial regulation made agrarian subjects knowable (Akpu n.d.).

What the archive does record with unusual clarity is the role of prison labour in establishing potato production at Jos and Mambila (Akpu n.d.). Seed potatoes were first cultivated by coerced workers under conditions of close administrative supervision in sites such as the Jos

Racecourse, mining camps, and government farms. This detail condenses the logic of colonial agricultural regulation. The crop that the state sought to diffuse among rural producers was first stabilised through coercion, and it was cultivated for consumers whom local farmers neither resembled nor primarily served. The organising principle of the scheme was therefore not Nigerian welfare, but imperial provisioning.

Colonial Regulatory Incoherence

The cases examined here suggest that colonial regulatory incoherence was not simply the result of institutional weakness or partial imitation. It was a structured effect of imperial rule. Guyer is right to show that regulatory forms travelled unevenly and that their breakdown helped erode the legitimacy of postcolonial states (Guyer 1993, 812–815). But the evidence assembled by Bonneuil, Chapman, and Akpu indicates that unevenness itself requires explanation. Colonial regimes imported the language and selected mechanisms of metropolitan regulation while withholding the institutional commitments that would have oriented those mechanisms toward local welfare.

Three dynamics were central to this incoherence. First, colonial regulation prioritised legibility and governability over protection. The “indigenous farm,” the monitored seed circuit, and the graded import regime were not designed to empower cultivators or consumers; they were designed to render agrarian production observable, comparable, and administratively manageable. Second, colonial seed policy disrupted existing systems of storage, exchange, and experimentation. By relocating seed into official channels, states weakened household autonomy and redirected agricultural reproduction toward export imperatives. Third, colonial and later postcolonial law systematically obscured the forms of labour and value that sustained agrarian diversity. Women’s seed work, collective experimentation, spiritual obligation, and ecologically situated judgment remained difficult to recognise within legal and scientific frameworks built around standardisation, ownership, and singular innovation (Bonneuil 1999, 291–296; Chapman 2022, 166–170).

Taken together, these dynamics explain why regulatory transfer repeatedly generated outcomes that appeared anomalous from the standpoint of metropolitan theory yet were entirely consistent with colonial objectives. The problem was not that colonial regimes failed to deliver the welfare they earnestly intended to provide. It was that welfare language, scientific authority, and administrative form were mobilised in support of extraction. Colonial regulation was incoherent only when judged against metropolitan ideals; viewed from the perspective of empire, its selectivity was functional.

Conclusion

Guyer observed in 1993 that former colonies often appeared to be operating “one model behind,” pursuing forms of food-security legitimation after Europe had moved toward new regulatory paradigms (Guyer 1993, 815). The cases examined here suggest a more precise formulation. Colonial and postcolonial seed regimes did not simply lag behind metropolitan developments; they preserved and recombined regulatory forms in ways that served extraction, administrative control, and external models of innovation. The adoption of intellectual property frameworks such as the Arusha Protocol in The Gambia demonstrates the continuing force of

this history (Chapman 2022, 166–170). Such regimes are readily legible to states, research institutions, and commercial actors, yet they remain poorly attuned to the social, moral, and ecological relations through which many farmers sustain varietal diversity.

Bonneuil notes the irony that colonial efforts to discipline local farming also contributed to later interest in indigenous knowledge (Bonneuil 1999, 299–300). But that afterlife should not obscure the asymmetry built into the original encounter. If Chapman’s account of rice innovation points toward an alternative regulatory imagination, it does so because it foregrounds shared credit, reciprocal obligation, and more-than-human participation rather than singular ownership and abstract legal entitlement (Chapman 2022, 167–170). Whether such systems can endure under expanding seed-law regimes remains uncertain. What is clear, however, is that any serious history of agricultural regulation in West Africa must treat the seed not only as a biological object or economic input but as a site at which power, knowledge, and social worlds were continually reorganised.

Bibliography

Primary sources

British Newspaper Archive (hereafter BNA), Off with their heads: Repressive culture in Northern Nigeria’ *Pall Mall Gazette*, 29 July 1912, p. 8.

Nigeria National Archives, Kaduna (hereafter NNAK), C.G. Ames, The Gazetteers of Plateau Province, 1932.

NNAK, Jos Prof. 3/1/1315, Memo on potato cultivation in the Northern provinces by P.H. Lamb, Director of Agriculture, Northern Province Zaria, 22 Nov. 1920.

NNAK, Yola Prof. 2303, District Officer, Biu Division to District Officer, Yola; Potatoes on Mambila Plateau, Mubi District, Verre District and Numan Division, 3 Oct. 1925.

NNAK, Yola Prof. 2303, Potatoes on Mambila Plateau, Mubi District, Verre District, and Numan Division.

NNAK, Jos Prof 3/1/1315, Resident Plateau Province to Governor of Nigeria, 1 June 1936.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 4922, Potatoes: Introduction and distribution of seed potatoes.

NNAK, Jos Prof 3/1/1315, Potato Cultivation in the Northern Provinces.

NNAK, Agric. Dept. 9314, H. Tempany at Colonial Office in London to J.R. Mackie, 2 Dec. 1942.

NNAK, Secretary Northern Provinces (hereafter SNP) Jos Prof 3/1/1315, Resident, Plateau Province to the Governor, 1 June 1936.

NNAK, Jos Prof 3/1/1091 Vol. II, Resident, Plateau Province to Food Controller, Lagos, 24 Nov. 1939.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 4921, Agricultural Officer, Samaru to the Resident, Plateau Province, 4 July 1940.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 3913, A.R. Carter, Commanding 89th W.A. Supply Platoon to Agricultural Officer at Riyom, 9 Nov. 1942.

Dry Eyes Now Seed Potatoes’, *Newcastle Journal and North Mail*, 11 November 1943, p. 4.

‘Seed Potato Tips for Colonies’, *The Mercury and Guardian*, 26 November 1943, p. 10.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 4924, Agricultural Officer, Samaru to Department of Agriculture in Northern Provinces Zaria: Scheme for selection and multiplication of disease-free seed, 1943.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 3913, Lt. R.T. Page to Asst. Director of Agriculture at Samaru, Military supplies: Potatoes, 21 April 1942.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 20135 Vol. IV, Senior Inspector of Produce, Northern District to Secretary Northern Provinces, 29 Aug. 1945.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 4922, Agricultural Officer to the D.O. Jos, Jemaa, and Pankshin, 20 Feb. 1946.

NNAK, Agric Dept. 4922, Ag. Principal Agric. Officer to Dept. of Agric, 21 Nov. 1947.

Society of African Missions Archive Cork (hereafter SMAAC), Irish Potatoes amongst the pagans, *The African Missionary* (hereafter *AM*), June-Aug. 1948, pp 11-2.

Secondary sources

Akpu, James. n.d. “Spuds and Empire: The Potato Scheme on the Mambila and Jos Plateaus in Northern Nigeria, 1923–1961.” Unpublished paper.

Bonneuil, Christophe. 1999. “Penetrating the Natives: Peanut Breeding, Peasants and the Colonial State in Senegal (1900–1950).” *Science, Technology and Society* 4 (2): 273–302.

Bourke, P.M. 1964. Emergence of potato blight. *Nature* 203:805- 808.

Chapman, Susannah. 2022. “The (In)visible Labour of Varietal Innovation.” In *Invisible Labour in Modern Science*, edited by Jenny Bangham, Judith Kaplan, and Xan Chacko, 163–172. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield.

Choiseul W, G. Doherty, et al., 2008. Potato varieties of historical interest in Ireland (Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, (DAFF).

Gilbert, A.W. 1920. *The Potato* (New York).

Harris David, Gordon C. Hillman. 2014. *Foraging and farming: The evolution of plant exploitation* (Oxfordshire).

Hugo Campos and Oscar Ortiz (eds). 2020. *The potato crop: Its agricultural, nutritional, and social contribution to humankind* (Switzerland: Springer).

Goshit Zakariya. 2000. “The evolution and spread of Irish potatoes cultivation in the Jos Plateau area of Nigeria, 1936-1960.” *The Nigerian Journal of Economic History*, (3): 1-15.

- Glendinning, D.R. 1983. 'Potato introductions and breeding up to the early 20th century', *New Phytol.* 94 (3): 479-505
- Guyer, Jane I. 1993. "'Toiling Ingenuity': Food Regulation in Britain and Nigeria." *American Ethnologist* 20 (4): 797–817.
- Hawkes J.G. and P. P. Hjerting. 1989. *The potatoes of Bolivia: Their breeding value and evolutionary relationships* (Oxford).
- McNeill, H. 2009. "The Introduction of the Potato into Ireland' *J. Modern History* 21.
- Nuijten, Edwin. 2005. *Farmer Management of Gene Flow: The Impact of Gender and Breeding System on Genetic Diversity and Crop Improvement in The Gambia*. PhD diss., Wageningen University.
- Obigbesan, G.O. 1976. Report on potato production in Nigeria: International potato course on production, storage, and seed technology (Wageningen, The Netherlands, International Agricultural Centre).
- van Loon J.P., E.T. Lammerts van Bueren, P.J. van Cruyningen, and J.S.C. Wiskerke, 2023. 'The history of Dutch potato breeding 1888-2018: From hobby to industry', *Potato Res.*
- Reader John. 2008. *Propitious Esculent: The Potato in World History* (London).
- Salaman, Redcliffe N.; Burton, W. G.; Hawkes, J. G. 1985. *The history and social influence of the potato* (Cambridge).
- Salaman, R.N. (ed.) 2009. *The History and Social Influence of the Potato* (London)
- Steele, W.M. 1967. "Agricultural Research in Kano." *Kano Studies* (3): 35.